

Achieving Climate Resilience through Genome Editing Technologies

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Abstract

The global human population is projected to reach about 10 billion by 2050. Keeping it in view, the two worldwide concerns are food security and climate change. Therefore, researchers aim for rapid, sustainable, and environmentally friendly advancements that improve "climate-resiliency" in crops within present agricultural techniques to increase food and nutritional security. As a result, since 2005, several genome-editing tools have been developed. It uses a variety of platforms, including CRISPR/Cas9 and CRISPR/Cpf1 and transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs), zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs), and transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs). The researchers have developed several climate-resilient crops: ease of use, high efficacy, precise changes at loci-of-interest, capacity to find novel features, and quick trait development.

Keywords- Genome Editing, Climate Resilience, CRISPR, Climate Change

Introduction

Genome editing, also known as gene editing, is a genetic engineering technique that primarily aids in inducing specific DNA changes, such as the insertion, deletion, or replacement of DNA through sequence-targeted recombination, which has accelerated the speed, simplicity, and reproducibility of making local DNA changes. Although GE technologies have progressed rapidly and have successfully been applied to a wide range of cells and organisms, there is a considerable variation in their cleavage efficiency at the target site. The primary mechanism involved in genome editing is double-stranded breaks (DSBs) in target site through programmed restriction endonucleases (FokI in Zinc finger and TALENs, Cas in CRISPR) followed by double strand breaks repair through homologous recombination (HR) or non-homologous end joining mechanism (NHEJ). Plants are modified by editing DNA bases at specific sites; hence edited plants can withstand a range of abiotic and biotic stresses such as salinity, drought, heat stress,

pests and diseases etc. It is one of the most powerful tools that can be used for developing climate-resilient plants; hence higher production can be achieved.

Genome editing tools:

1). Zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs) were first discovered in sequence-specific eukaryotic transcription factors. ZFNs are chimeric proteins with a DNA cleavage domain of the FokI restriction endonuclease (a bacterial protein) and an array of three or four zinc fingers. The DNA binding domain of the first eukaryotic sequence-specific transcription factor was discovered to have zinc-binding repeats. Each zinc finger motif can recognize three to four bases of sequence. With the combined recognition specificity of 18 nucleotide sequences, a ZFN pair may distinguish between two neighboring DNA sequences on opposing strands.

2). Transcription Activator-Like Effectors (TALEs) and the FokI endonuclease make up Transcription Activator-Like Effector Nucleases (TALENs), also known as transcription activator-like effector nucleases. Bacterial pathogens that infect plants produce TALE proteins to influence the host transcription system and facilitate effective infection. Similar to ZFNs, TALENs work in pairs to make a particular break at a DNA sequence that the TALE domain recognizes. With a tandem array of 16 (or more) substantially identical protein modules that each target a single nucleotide at the DNA target site, TALENs for DNA recognition have a precise mechanism.

3). CRISPR/Cas system) Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats: this is an easier and more efficient genome editing tool than engineered ZFNs and TALENs. Short foreign DNA segments, known as "spacers," are inserted within the CRISPR genomic locus and then translated and processed into short CRISPR RNA by the CRISPR/Cas system (crRNA). These crRNAs anneal to transactivating crRNAs (tracrRNAs), triggering sequence-specific Cas protein cleavage and silencing of pathogenic DNA. Recent research has demonstrated that the Cas9 protein needs a "seed" sequence within the crRNA and a conserved protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) upstream of the crRNA binding region to recognize targets. Altering the crRNA, the CRISPR/Cas system may be directed to break almost any DNA sequence. Cas 9 nucleases can be designed to cleave at a specific place, making this tool extremely precise.

Genome editing implication in crop improvement

- The genome-edited plants have been modified to tolerate a variety of biotic challenges, including insects, diseases, and weeds, as well as abiotic conditions like heat, cold, salt, drought, flood, and pollution.
- Genetic improvement of crop plants can be achieved without using transgenic organisms by utilizing a breeding technique that uses gene editing technologies to knock down transcription factors.
- Crops generated by genome editing will be crucial in boosting crop output and solving the

global problem of ensuring adequate food and nutrition. As a result, this talk emphasises utilising all genome-editing methods and their application in the creation of climate-resilient agriculture.

- Genome editing technology is more accurate than conventional breeding since it only creates mutations in the target gene without changing background genes.
- Genome editing technologies with variable degrees of success provide simple-to-design, affordable tools for accurate and successful plant genome editing. They have also become more potent tools in recent years, allowing for the targeted modification of plants through directed mutagenesis and the development of varieties with improved quality and resistance to stress that are useful for various applications.

Conclusion

GE is an effective method for creating novel plant species with specified agronomic characteristics and nutritional value. To advance their application in plant breeding programmes and commercial-scale production, GE elite plants having specified gene mutation(s) without foreign DNA may help boost public acceptance of agricultural goods and free them from regulatory oversight. Plant systems can be especially appealing for testing novel ideas and developing new strategies in GE-related research that aims to increase the accuracy, adaptability, and efficiency of these molecular tools and apply them with ease to other systems because they are relatively inexpensive to maintain, have short generation cycles, and are easier to handle than animals. However, the absence of rules and the ambiguity surrounding potential applications could hinder the use of GE to improve plants. However, for the time being, this research is typically placed on hold while waiting for new rules and accurate assessments of GE technologies used for plant improvement. Researchers have the knowledge and resources to utilise these new tools for the introduction of new traits into plants.

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